

A CASE STUDY ON MUKADOOSHIKA

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Article Received on 15 Dec. 2025,
Article Revised on 05 Jan. 2026,
Article Published on 16 Jan. 2026

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18266091>

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How to cite this Article: ¹Dr. Radhika Ranjan Geethesh P., ^{2*}Dr. Sindhuri. (2026) A CASE STUDY ON MUKADOOSHIKA. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 15(2), 923-927.

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ABSTRACT

Mukhadushika is a common dermatological disorder described in Ayurvedic classics under Kṣudra Roga, characterized by pidika resembling shalmali-kaṇṭaka occurring predominantly on the face of adolescents and young adults. It closely correlates with Acne Vulgaris in modern dermatology, a chronic inflammatory disease of the pilosebaceous unit. According to Ayurveda, Mukhaduṣhika arises due to the vitiation of Kapha, Vata, and Rakta doṣa, with the involvement of Meda dhatu and Svedavaha srotas, precipitated by factors such as improper diet, hormonal changes, stress, and poor lifestyle practices. Clinically, it presents with papules, pustules, nodules, and sometimes scarring, leading to cosmetic disfigurement and psychological distress. Contemporary management mainly focuses on topical and systemic agents, which often produce adverse effects and recurrence. Ayurvedic

management emphasizes nidana parivarjana, shodhana therapies like Vamana and Raktamokṣaṇa, and shamana measures using herbal formulations possessing lekhana, raktaprasadana, kledahara, and shothahara properties. This holistic approach not only addresses the symptoms but also corrects the underlying doṣhik imbalance, offering a safer and sustainable therapeutic alternative. The present abstract highlights the Ayurvedic perspective, etiopathogenesis, and integrative management of Mukhadushika in correlation with Acne vulgaris.

KEYWORDS: Mukadooshika, Acne vulgaris, Shamana, Dosha.

INTRODUCTION

Acne vulgaris is a follicular disorder affecting susceptible pilosebaceous follicles, primarily of the face, neck, and upper trunk and characterized by both non-inflammatory and inflammatory lesions. It is one of the most common dermatoses affecting the teenage population. Boys have a peak incidence between ages of 16 and 19 years and girls between ages of 14 and 16 years. Both sexes are equally affected. Most cases of acne subside completely within a few years of their onset but a small percentage continue to remain active.

Acne vulgaris is a dermatosis of unknown etiology. However, many factors are incriminated in its pathogenesis and aggravation. Andro-genic stimulation at puberty is believed to increase the activity of sebaceous glands and sebum production. A change in the process of keratinization of the sebaceous follicle may produce an increased adherence of the horn cells resulting in retention hyperkeratosis. Free fatty acids in the surface lipids are also suspected to be comedogenic. Bacterial colonization of the sebaceous follicle may also contribute in the pathogenesis of acne.^[1]

Ayurvedic classics explain Mukadushika in the context of Kshudraroga which is caused by the vitiation of Kapha, Vata and Raktha resulting in the formation of Shalmalikantakavath Pidaka on face along with Ruja.^[2]

CASE REPORT

On 9 November 2024 a hindu male 19year old, non diabetic, not a known case of hypertension, visited Out Patient department of Sri Dharmasthala Manjunatheshwara College of Ayurveda Udupi, with the complaints stated below.

Chief complaints

Complaints of multiple pimples on bilateral cheeks and forehead region since 6 months.

History of present illness

Patient was said to be asymptomatic 6 months back. Gradually he developed with multiple achne lesions over bilateral cheeks and forehead region. Initialy the lesions were small comedones/papules, which later progressed to inflammatory pustules which is associated with pain. He had taken the treatment from a General physician but found no complete relief, then he came here for further management.

Personal history

Patient is Cricket player with a mixed type of dietary habit.

General examination

General condition- Good

RS- NAD

CVS- S1 S2 NAD; No added sounds

CNS- NAD

P/A- Soft

BP- 130/80mmHg

Pulse- 80/min

Moderately built with no other systemic illness.

Prakriti - Kapha- Vataja

Vikriti - Kapha-Vata

Sara - Madhyama

Samhanana - Madhyama

Pramana - Madhyama

Satwa - Madhyama

Satmya - Madhyama

Ahara shakthi - Madhyama

Vyayama shakti- Madhyama

Local examination

Type of lesion was papules and pustules

Colour was Reddish and skin at the site of lesions were hard.

Pain and tenderness are present at the site of lesions

- *Dosha- Kapha Pradhana Tridosha*
- *Dushya- Twak, Ratka*
- *Agni- Mandagni*
- *Srotas- Rakta vaha srotas*
- *Nidana- Virudhaahara, Divaswapna, Atisevana of Dadhi, Athi madhura and amla ahara sevana and intake of fried food*

Samprapti

Due to above said Nidana; it vitiates the Dushya like Twak, Rakta resulting in the Lakshana like Pidaka, Shotha, Raga and Ruja

Diagnosis- Mukadooshika

TREATMENT**Oral Medications**

Yeshtimadhu capsule 1-1-1
 Shodak syrup 10ml- 10ml- 10ml
 Sariva kalpa 10ml-10ml-10ml x 30 days; After food

External Medications

Mukadoshihara lepa - application on face for once a day morning
 Nirmal bath powder - application on face for once a day afternoon

D-Sora soap for bathing

Siddharthaka snana choorna for bathing to apply on all the lesions half an hour before bath

Special note- Patient is advised to take light food throughout the treatment period, avoid *Nidana* and maintain proper hygiene in the working environment.

Table 1: Outcomes.

Parameter	Before treatment	15 th day of treatment	30 th day of treatment
Redness	Present	Reduced	Absent
Papules	Present	Slightly reduced	Reduced
Pustules	Present	Reduced	Absent
Itching	Slightly present	Absent	Absent

Medicines were continued for 1 month again after the 30th day follow-up.

DISCUSSION

Mukadushika is a commonly encountered Ksudra Roga described in Ayurvedic classics, predominantly affecting the Muka pradesha of adolescents and young adults, arising due to the vitiation of Kapha, Vata and Rakta dosha with significant involvement of Pitta in inflammatory stages.^[3] Management of Mukhadushika in Ayurveda emphasizes Nidhana parivarjana, Shodhana and Shamana chikitsa. This study highlights the importance of Samana chikitsa in the effective management of Mukadushika. Shodhak syrup is a proprietary

ayurvedic medicine contains Manjishta and Pancha nimba choorna helps in reducing the infection and act as a blood purifier.^[4] Sariva kalpa is an arishta preparation that functions as a blood purifier due to its kandgna and kushtagna properties.^[5] Yeshtimadhu is another effective drug endowed with vranaropana, shothahara and medhya property. Acharya Bavaprakasha mentioned yeshtimadhu as best pitta anila asrdoshahara and varnya.^[6] External applicants like Mukadooshikari lepa^[7], Nirmal bath powder, D-Sora soap for bathing and Siddharthaka snana choorna acts as cleanser, relieves acne and pimples, improve skin complexion and texture.

CONCLUSION

In the present study drug and formulations employed in Shamana chikitsa help in Dosha shaman, Rakthaprasadhana, Shothahara and Vranaropana, thereby reducing inflammation, pain, suppuration and post lesional scarring. Internal medication along with external applications act synergistically to purify the channels, normalize Agni, and restore the health of skin. Moreover Shamana chikitsa is safe, cost-effective and suitable for long term use, making it preferable option in the management of Mukhadushika.

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